

Review Article

Transfer of arrhythmia substrate targets from the cardiac electroanatomical and imaging modalities to the planning computed tomography scan for stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation for refractory ventricular tachycardia – a state-of-the-art review on software developments on behalf of the STOPSTORM.eu consortium

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Abbreviations: AHA, American heart association; CA, catheter ablation; CardTV-EP, “2D” cardiac target volume defined by invasive or non-invasive electrophysiological data; CardTV, final cardiac target volume defined by electrophysiological and imaging data; CardTV-IMG, cardiac target volume potentially encompassing the arrhythmia substrate defined by imaging data; CardTV-RT, cardiac target volume as indicated on the planning CT after multidisciplinary consent; CCTA, cardiac computed tomography angiography; CE, conformité Européenne; COM, center of mass; CT, computed tomography; DICOM, digital imaging and communications in medicine; DICOM-RT, DICOM radiotherapy; DICOM RTSS, DICOM radiotherapy structure set; DICOM SEG, DICOM segmentation; EAM, electroanatomical map; ECGI, electrocardiographic imaging; FDA, food and drug administration; ICD, implantable cardioverter-defibrillator; ITV, internal target volume; LGE, late gadolinium enhancement; LV, left ventricle; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; NICM, non-ischemic cardiomyopathy; PCT, planning CT; PET, Positron emission tomography; PTV, planning target volume; QA, quality assurance; SBRT, stereotactic body radiotherapy; SPECT, single photon emission CT; STAR, stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation; STOPSTORM.eu, Standardized Treatment and Outcome Platform for Stereotactic Therapy of Re-entrant tachycardia by a Multidisciplinary consortium; TPS, treatment planning system; VT, ventricular tachycardia.

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ABSTRACT

Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) for ventricular tachycardia (VT) is a non-invasive treatment modality to reduce the VT burden by delivering a single high radiation dose to the arrhythmogenic substrate. Identification and delineation of the arrhythmogenic substrate, definition of the radiation target, and transfer of this target across different imaging modalities from the invasive electroanatomic map (EAM) to the planning computed tomography (CT) scan are key to the success of therapeutic radiation. The VT substrate is identified using EAM data and co-localized with radiological correlates of the ventricular scar. Precise transfer to the non-ECG-gated treatment planning CT is essential for safe and effective STAR delivery.

Current challenges include translating the endocardial or epicardial EAM surface target into a 3D cardiac target volume (CTV), reconciling different acquisition methods (e.g., (exhale-gated) EAM, contrast-enhanced ECG-gated CT angiography, and non-gated non-contrast planning CT), and achieving accurate CTV transfer using multi-modal image integration. Early approaches relied on manual delineation using side-by-side EAM and CT rendering, leading to poor reproducibility and potential treatment failure. Emerging (semi)auto-segmentation software based on the American Heart Association (AHA) 17-segment left ventricular model offers promise but lacks standardized weighing of identified segments and methods for handling partially involved segments. More recently, 2D-to-3D and 3D-to-3D target transfer methods, including commercial and in-house computer-aided tools, have been developed to address these difficulties. Currently, a standardized workflow has not been established.

This review addresses the need to standardize CTV definitions and transfer workflows, assessing available tools and proposing quality assurance measures based on recommendations of the [STOPSTORM.eu](https://www.stopstorm.eu) consortium.

Introduction

Ventricular tachycardia (VT) is a major cause of cardiovascular death in patients with structural heart disease. [1,2] Standard treatments include antiarrhythmic drugs, implantable cardioverter-defibrillators (ICDs), and catheter ablation(s). [2,3] While catheter ablation is more effective than antiarrhythmic drugs in reducing VT episodes, ICD shocks, and hospitalizations, [4,5] over one-third of patients experience VT recurrences within 30 months. [4].

Stereotactic body radiotherapy (SBRT), originally developed for solid tumors, has recently been adapted as stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) for the treatment of recurrent VT unresponsive to conventional therapies. This approach is particularly valuable for patients with inaccessible arrhythmia substrates or those ineligible for catheter ablation, such as cases with intramural substrates or double mechanical valves. STAR typically delivers a single dose of 25 Gy to the arrhythmogenic substrate, defined as the cardiac target volume (CardTV) on the radiation oncologist's planning computed tomography (PCT) scan. [6–8] Following early investigations, [9] its short- and medium-term safety and efficacy were demonstrated by Cuculich et al. [10] and further validated in subsequent clinical trials. [11,12].

Successful STAR planning includes accurate CardTV delineation in the PCT (CardTV-RT), requiring multidisciplinary collaboration among electrophysiologists, imaging specialists, radiation oncologists, and medical physicists. Given cardiac and respiratory organ motion, as well as intrinsic inaccuracies of radiotherapy delivery, safety margins must be applied to the CardTV-RT according to institutionally established motion-management strategies. [13] To account for cardiac motion, the cardiac internal target volume (ITV) can be derived from magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA). [14,15] Respiratory-motion management—well established in radiation oncology—can involve respiratory gating, tracking, or 4DCT-based respiratory ITV creation, with the final planned target volume (PTV) determined based on institutional preferences and available breathing-motion management techniques. Since motion in scarred myocardium is relatively small, and dedicated motion studies remain limited, most prospective trials recommend a CTV-PTV margin of 5 mm

to cover both cardiac motion and other influences, while avoiding nearby organs at risk. [13,16,17].

Accurate and reproducible extrapolation of the arrhythmogenic substrate (CardTV) from the “2D” endocardial and/or epicardial electroanatomical mapping (CardTV-EP) into a 3D transmural volume on the CT and transfer to the treatment planning system (TPS) are essential for quality assurance, minimizing arrhythmia recurrences, and reducing radiation toxicity. [15,18,19] This process may involve co-localization with radiological determinants of ventricular scar (CardTV-IMG). Various target transfer workflows and semi-automated tools integrating electrophysiological and imaging-based substrates have been developed, though their accuracy and reproducibility vary (Graphical Abstract). [6,20–26] As STAR continues to evolve, standardization of the CardTV delineation and transfer process remains crucial. This review provides an overview of the currently available commercial and in-house computer-aided software solutions, highlights accuracy requirements, and emphasizes the need for standardized reporting, as recommended by the [STOPSTORM.eu](https://www.stopstorm.eu) consortium. [15].

Cardiac target volume definition

Electrophysiological CTV delineation (CardTV-EP)

Ventricular arrhythmogenesis in structural heart disease and the invasive catheter-based identification of the 2D CardTV-EP_{inv} are extensively detailed in the 2024 EHRA/HRS consensus statement. [27] In brief, VT usually results from reentrant excitation involving myocardial regions with slowed conduction, typically in scar tissue. Abnormal refractoriness of diseased myocardium facilitates reentry depending on the conduction velocity of the surviving fibers and the circuit size. A protected isthmus, consisting of strands of surviving myocardium bounded by non-excitabile scar, can slow conduction and force the wavefront to travel a path of a defined length. [28] This isthmus is not only a necessary prerequisite for reentry, but also the target for interventions. It can be identified during ongoing VT using entrainment or activation mapping techniques. Once the reentry circuit and the critical isthmus have been elucidated, radiofrequency delivery at the critical site can terminate the VT, thereby confirming the putative mechanism. [29] In cases of hemodynamic instability, VT non-inducibility, or inducibility of non-clinical VTs, surrogate markers (e.

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g., voltage mapping, pace mapping, functional substrate mapping, or electrogram morphology assessment) are used to characterize and target the arrhythmogenic substrate. [27].

Non-invasive electrocardiographic (ECG) techniques, including the standard 12-lead ECG and ECG-imaging (ECGI), offer insights into the clinical VT exit localization but lack the spatial resolution needed to precisely identify VT targets or isthmus sites. Additionally, ECGI has significant methodological limitations in accurately localizing septal VT exits. [30] Given the limited data on the efficacy and safety of non-invasive electrophysiological delineation for STAR, current consensus is to not rely solely on non-invasive imaging for identifying CardTV-EP in both ischemic and non-ischemic (NICM) substrates. [26,31,32] However, non-invasive mapping may be useful when invasive substrate characterization is not feasible, such as in unstable patients or those with thrombus or double mechanical valves.

Imaging-based CTV delineation (CardTV-IMG)

Following a comprehensive evaluation of CardTV-EP_{inv}, supplemented by the CardTV-EP_{non-inv}, the arrhythmogenic VT substrate (CardTV-EP) is identified on the 2D surface of the electroanatomical map (EAM). [10,26] Additional structural imaging techniques, such as cardiac MRI, CCTA, or nuclear scintigraphy (CardTV-IMG), can further refine the arrhythmia substrate and facilitate its transmural extension into a target volume (CardTV), while also delineating adjacent structures, including valves, vessels or nerves. [33–35].

Cardiac MRI

Cardiac MRI with late gadolinium enhancement (LGE), the gold standard for imaging myocardial fibrosis, [36] can identify heterogeneous tissue channels—isolated strips of border-zone tissue that connect healthy myocardium separated by fibrosis. These channels have been linked to critical VT isthmuses and correlate with arrhythmia substrate markers, such as abnormal electrograms and deceleration zones. [37–39] LGE MRI may aid in CardTV-IMG delineation for post-myocardial infarction patients. However, its role in NICM is limited due to variable pixel-signal intensity cut-offs and low accuracy in characterising diffuse fibrosis. T1 mapping may enhance interstitial fibrosis detection but has a lower spatial resolution. [40] Additional limitations include reduced diagnostic yield in patients with ICDs due to device-related artifacts (even with wide-band sequences) and contraindications for those with MRI-incompatible devices.

CCTA

The value of CCTA in STAR planning lies in its high-resolution assessment of regional myocardial wall thickness, crucial for substrate refinement, CardTV-EP transmural extension, and visualization of adjacent cardiovascular structures. CCTA can identify channels of preserved wall thickness within severely thinned ventricular regions (<5 mm), which are associated with VT isthmuses and functional substrates. [41–43] Late-iodine enhancement CT, requiring additional or larger contrast injections and postprocessing techniques, may enhance the distinction between ventricular scar and healthy tissue, showing strong correlation with reduced bipolar EAM voltages in post-myocardial infarction and NICM patients. [41,44] The CardTV-IMG can complement CardTV-EP and aid in the transmural CardTV generation either using a side-by-side comparison or 2D/3D co-registration. Additionally, CCTA can assess coronary artery patency and trajectory, detect myocardial calcification and fatty infiltration, and exclude intracavitary thrombus or adjacent lung disease. [45–47].

Its advantages—short acquisition times, accessibility, high temporal and spatial resolution, compatibility with ICD patients, and reduced susceptibility to device-related artifacts—generally outweigh concerns regarding radiation exposure and contrast media administration. Notably, CCTA is less prone to streak artifacts from cardiac implantable device leads compared to MRI.

Nuclear scintigraphy

Although its role has diminished with advancements in MRI and CCTA, nuclear imaging provides insights into scar viability, inflammation, and sympathetic denervation. Correlations between single photon emission CT (SPECT)/positron emission tomography (PET) abnormalities and VT isthmuses suggest potential value, but further validation is needed. [48,49].

CardTV transfer into the planning CT scan

Once the CardTV is defined, it must be accurately and reproducibly transferred to the non-ECG-triggered treatment planning CT system in order to ensure safe and effective STAR delivery. Key challenges include converting the CardTV-EP from a curved endo- or epicardial surface in EAM space into a transmural target volume in CT space, reconciling different acquisition methods (e.g., exhale-gated EAM, contrast-enhanced ECG-gated CCTA, and non-gated PCT), and achieving precise CardTV transfer via multi-modal image co-registration. Registration accuracy may be compromised by incomplete anatomical mapping during EAM. [50].

CardTV delineation and transfer accuracy can be evaluated using a suite of geometric methods. [51] The frequently-used Dice coefficient, a similarity metric that quantifies volumetric overlap. It is calculated as twice the overlapping volume divided by the sum of both volumes. [52] The American Association of Physicists in Medicine recommends a Dice similarity coefficient of 0.8–0.9 for assessing deformable image registration performance. [52] Other methods include the average and maximum boundary (Hausdorff) distances, the added path length, and the surface Dice similarity coefficient.

As no standardized approach for CardTV transfer exists, various 2D-to-3D and 3D-to-3D methods, including commercial and in-house computer-aided tools, as well as manual transfer have been developed (Table 1). All commercial and non-commercial solutions discussed below are currently not FDA (Food and Drug Administration) or CE (Conformité Européenne) marked for STAR planning and transfer, and therefore these tools are only used in a research capacity. This section discusses these CardTV transfer techniques, their technical aspects, accuracy, and cross-validation results.

Manual delineation

In the early stages of STAR development, CardTV-EP was manually delineated on CCTA or PCT using CardioPlan within the radiotherapy treatment planning system [53] or by visually comparing the EAM with the 3D-rendered segmented CT (“eyeballing”). [11] Anatomical landmarks such as the aortic root, aortic valve, coronary arteries, and coronary sinus, along with non-anatomical references like the ICD lead, were used for guidance.

However, this approach had significant limitations. The inability to measure distances consistently across modalities and the intracavitary mobility of the ICD lead contributed to inaccuracies in target transfer. Additionally, aligning 2D EAM-derived surfaces with sagittal, coronal, or axial CT planes proved complex and error-prone. Consequently, manual delineation resulted in low interobserver and inter-institutional reproducibility, even among experienced staff. [22,23] The variability in 3D center-of-mass (COM) differences reached up to 3.5 cm, and Dice coefficients for manually transferred structures ranged from just 0.02 to 0.31. [22,23] Interobserver agreement showed significant discrepancies, with CardTV variations up to 100 % and COM localization differences exceeding 6 mm. Such inaccuracies likely contributed to treatment failures, necessitating redo-catheter ablation or STAR. [18,23,53,68].

Later, Wight et al. developed a MATLAB application for 3D representation and manual EAM substrate registration to PCT. [69] CardTV-RT contouring was performed directly in the TPS using a side-by-side approach.

Table 1
Overview of key characteristics of CardTV transfer workflows.

	Workflow	Commercial availability	Supp. imaging modalit.	Platform	Interobs. accuracy	Cross valid.	EAM vendor	Advantages	Limitations	Ref.
Side-by-side CardTV transfer	Manual delineation	No	EAM, CCTA, 12-lead ECG	None	DSC 0.02–0.31, COM differences 3.5 cm	Na	All	– Low cost – No additional software required – No image co-registration	– Orientation difficulties – Unacceptably high interobserver and inter-institutional variation – Possible suboptimal outcome due to mistargeting (VT relapse and/or toxicity)	[11,22,23]
	CardioPlan	Yes	EAM, PCT	CardioPlan (Cyberheart)	Na	Na	All	– Low cost – No additional software required	– Orientation difficulties – No input from MRI, CCTA, or nuclear scintigraphy	[53]
	Wight	No	EAM, PCT	MATLAB	Na	Na	CARTO, EnSite NavX/Precision	– No image co-registration needed	– Orientation difficulties – No input from MRI, CCTA, or nuclear scintigraphy – Not compatible with RHYTHMIA	55]
	17-AHA segment	No	EAM, CCTA, SPECT, MRI, ECGI, 12-lead ECG	Segmental heatmap	DSC 0.31–0.80, interobserver root mean square distance of structures 5.1 mm	Na	All	– No image co-registration needed – Standardization is available	–Time-intensive and complex –Highly reliant on user expertise –Generation of heatmap lacks standardization – Prone to result in larger target volumes – No validation for ventricular aneurysmal remodelling – Segmentation of right ventricle is not supported	[6,10,11,23,26,54–56]
2D-to-3D	CARDIO-RT	No, software available upon request	EAM screen shots, CCTA	MATLAB	Na	Yes, COM difference 3.6 mm and DSC 0.84	All	– User-friendly interface – Fast transfer – High accuracy – Quality assurance – Cross validated	– Requires certain level of expertise – No option to integrate MRI, ECGI or nuclear scintigraphy – No analysis of CT- or MRI-derived wall thickness/channels	[22,25,57,58]
3D-to-3D	EAMapReader	No, software available online	EAM, CCTA	Python, 3D Slicer	Na	Yes, COM difference 3.6 mm, DSC 0.84	All	– Quality assurance – High accuracy	– Labor intensive – Requires basic knowledge of coding – No analysis of CT- or MRI-derived wall thickness/channels – No option to integrate ECGI	[20,58]

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Table 1 (continued)

Workflow	Commercial availability	Supp. imaging modalit.	Platform	Interobs. accuracy	Cross valid.	EAM vendor	Advantages	Limitations	Ref.
HeartMap	No	EAM, CCTA, MRI, ECGI	Python, 3D Slicer (extension for HeartMap)	DSC 0.71	Na	CARTO	– Supports integration of ECGI and MRI	– Cannot integrate .vtk files – Requires basic knowledge of coding	[28]
Brett	No, code available online	EAM, CCTA	HeartMap, 3D Slicer, visual toolkit script	Na	Na	CARTO	– Open access	– No option to integrate MRI, derived wall thickness/channels – EnSite NavX/Precision or RHYTHMIA HDx not supported – No analysis of CT- or MRI-derived wall thickness/channels	[21]
MIM	No	EAM, CCTA, MRI, PCT	MATLAB, MIM Maestro	DSC 0.81	Na	CARTO	– Direct integration EAM in PCT – High accuracy	– No option to integrate ECGI – EnSite NavX/Precision or RHYTHMIA HDx not supported – No open access – No analysis of CT- or MRI-derived wall thickness/channels	[59]
CardioMerge	No	EAM, CCTA, SPECT, respiratory CT	C#, insight and visualization toolkit	DSC 0.62–0.81	Na	CARTO	– Analysis of CT-derived wall thickness.	– EnSite NavX/Precision or RHYTHMIA HDx not supported – No open-access – No option to integrate MRI or ECGI	[60,61]
Dvorak	No	EAM, CCTA, PCT	C#, visualization toolkit, 3D Slicer	Na	Na	CARTO	– Integration of additional anatomical and functional information	– EnSite NavX/Precision or RHYTHMIA HDx not supported – Requires basic knowledge of coding – No open-access	[62]
Edico	No	EAM, PCT	MATLAB and Python script for EAM integration in TPS	DSC 0.87–0.96	Na	CARTO	– Direct registration of EAM to PCT – High interobserver similarity	– Not compatible with RHYTHMIA or EnSite NavX/Precision – No input from MRI, nuclear scintigraphy – Orientation difficulties – No DICOM standard for EAM – No analysis of CT- or MRI-derived wall thickness/channels	[63]
ADAS3D	Yes	EAM, CCTA, MRI, ECGI, PCT	ADAS3D	Hausdorff distance 3.6 mm [2.7–4.5]	Na	All	– Integration of additional anatomical (wall thickness, channels) and functional information	– High cost – No open access – No integration of SPECT	[26,64]

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Table 1 (continued)

Workflow	Commercial availability	Supp. imaging modalit.	Platform	Interobs. accuracy	Cross valid.	EAM vendor	Advantages	Limitations	Ref.
InHEART	Yes	CCTA, MRI	Online twinning platform (MUSIC), side-by-side or 3D Slicer	Na	Na	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Steep learning curve – Fast < 30 min – High interobserver agreement – Little expertise required – Integration of additional anatomical and functional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High cost per case – No open access – Multiple integration steps – No information on CardTV-IMG definition – No user-dependent modulation possible – No integration of EAM, SPECT, ECGI 	[65]
MIMICs Innovation Suite	Yes	EAM, CCTA, ECGI	Online platform	Na	Na	Not reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Little expertise required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High cost – No open access – No additional anatomical information – Does not import.mesh files – No integration of MRI or SPECT 	[66]
HoloLens Integration	Yes	EAM, CCTA	HoloLens 2	Na	Na	CARTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 3D visual representation to facilitate interdisciplinary communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Requires high computing power – EnSite NavX/Precision or RHYTHMIA HDx not supported 	[67]

Abbreviations: AHA, American Heart Association; CardTV, cardiac target volume; CardTV-IMG, cardiac target volume potentially encompassing the arrhythmia substrate defined by imaging data; CCTA, cardiac computed tomography; CTV_{EP}, electrophysiologically-defined arrhythmogenic ventricular tachycardia substrate; DSC, Dice coefficient of similarity; EAM, electroanatomic mapping; ECGI, electrocardiographic imaging; ITV, internal target volume; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; Na, not available; PCT, planning CT; PTV, planning target volume; SPECT, single-photon emission CT; STAR, stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation; TPS, treatment planning system; VT, ventricular tachycardia.

17-American Heart Association segmental workflow

To improve interdisciplinary communication in STAR target volume definition, the 17-segment left ventricular (LV) model from the AHA has been integrated into EAM and PCT workflows. [6,10,54] Brownstein et al. proposed a step-by-step framework to reorient the heart in CCTA from orthogonal to cardiac-oriented views, enabling structured identification of the 17 segments. [54] This model divides the LV into thirds along its long axis (base to apex), further subdivided into 4–6 circumferential sections, with the 17th segment representing the apex (Fig. 1).

Some groups have applied this 17-segment approach to define CardTV, aggregating, but not co-registering, CardTV-IMG with or without arrhythmogenic segments from CardTV-EP into a ‘heatmap’ (Fig. 1, Panel A-D, as depicted in ADAS). [10,23] This workflow is complementary to CardTV-EP. However, the methodology for selecting arrhythmogenic segments across imaging modalities remains unclear. This segmental heatmap is ultimately referenced in the PCT. The 17-segment AHA model is currently used in the largest, ongoing prospective study that randomises patients with high-risk, refractory VT to either STAR or catheter ablation (RADIATE-VT, NCT05765175).

Despite its structured nature, segmentation of the 17 segments on traditional body axes is time-intensive, complex, and highly dependent on user expertise, leading to significant interobserver variability. In one study, segmental delineation by two electrophysiologists yielded a mean Dice coefficient as low as 0.31 ± 0.21 . [23] Additionally, this workflow lacks validation for patient-specific ventricular aneurysmal remodelling and does not support segmentation of outflow tracts or right ventricular regions. Handling of partially involved segments is unclear.

As with EAM-to-TPS transfer tools, automated segmentation is advancing and now outperforms previous methods. An in-house semi-automated segmentation tool has demonstrated improved reproducibility, achieving a median Dice coefficient of 0.8 (interquartile range:

0.70–0.87). [55].

Another solution, the stand-alone in-house developed CARDIO-RT research software (Institute of Robotics and Cognitive Systems of the University of Luebeck, Germany), [25] enables landmark-based generation of the 17-segment bullseye model from CCTA (Fig. 1, Panel E). This approach uses three anatomical landmarks—the aortic valve center, mitral valve center, and LV apex—anchoring the aortic valve center for rotation around the LV long axis.

Recently, Morris introduced automated 17-segment segmentation. [56] Here, the physician defines the LV long axis, and the software generates the 17 LV segments in under five minutes—compared to two hours for manual segmentation—providing an efficient and reliable method for target generation.

2D-to-3D registration workflow

The CARDIO-RT research-software facilitates 2D-to-3D registration of segmented endocardial and epicardial ventricular contours from CCTA with corresponding 2D EAM screenshots of the arrhythmogenic CardTV-EP, using standardized anatomical views (e.g., anteroposterior, right anterior oblique, left anterior oblique, and superior; Fig. 2, Panels A and B). [22,25,57] Screenshots from various EAM systems can be used for registration, including CARTO® 3 (Biosense Webster, Johnson & Johnson Medical, Irvine, CA, USA), EnSite™ NavX™/Velocity™/Precision™ (Abbott, St. Paul, MN, USA), and RHYTHMIA HDx™ (Boston Scientific, Marlborough, MA, USA). For 2D-to-3D registration, planar projections of the CCTA-segmented contours are overlaid onto the EAM screenshots. A 2D polygon is generated on these planar projections, aligning with the previously delineated CardTV-EP from the EAM screenshots. Anatomical landmarks can serve as validation points.

Points within this polygon on the endocardial/epicardial contours are defined as VT target points in Digital Imaging and Communications

Fig. 1. 17-American Heart Association (AHA) segmental model depicted in ADAS3D and CARDIO-RT workflows. Panel A. Within ADAS3D, (semi)automated segmentation of the left ventricle can be performed and visualized on the cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA), magnetic resonance imaging, electrocardiographic imaging, and electroanatomic map (EAM). In this case, areas of wall thinning (CCTA) and reduced peak-to-peak bipolar voltages (EAM) span segments 8, 13, 14, and 17. Adapted from Kaya et al. with permission. [26] Panel B. Localization of the ventricular tachycardia (VT) exit as determined by the QRS morphology from the 12-lead ECG and potentially ECG-imaging (segments 13, 14, 15, 17). Panel C. VT isthmus (and exit) localization with invasive electroanatomic mapping (segments 8-13-14). Panel D. The electrophysiologically defined arrhythmogenic VT substrate (CardTV-EP, in blue) can be indicated on the 17-AHA segmental model using a so-called ‘heatmap’, here displayed in ADAS. This workflow is limited by the potential entire covering of partially diseased segments, resulting in larger target volumes. Panel E. CARDIO-RT AHA 17-segment model registration process using the aorta (black) as the registration reference. Left ventricular segments are shown in different colors. Abbreviations as in the Graphical Abstract: LAT, local activation time. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. 2D-to-3D transfer of the EAM target surface to the cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA) by CARDIO-RT. **Panel A.** Electroanatomic map (EAM) screenshot showing the CardTV-EP in the left lateral view (yellow). **Panel B.** After fusion of the EAM with the CCTA-derived left-ventricular and aortic volumes, the CardTV-EP can be extended transmurally. **Panel C.** CardTV-EP in different CCTA views. Abbreviations as in the Graphical Abstract. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

in Medicine (DICOM)-conformant file format and extended transmurally using a radial margin and overlap function to the previously segmented LV myocardium to generate the final CardTV (Fig. 2, Panel C). The resulting CardTV is saved in DICOM-Radiotherapy Structure Set (RTSS) format, referencing to the CCTA. After co-registering the CCTA with the PCT, the CardTV can be accurately transferred to the PCT for further treatment planning.

3D-to-3D registration workflows

Recent advancements in 3D-to-3D registration software aim to enhance the accuracy of transferring the CardTV to the PCT to derive the CardTV-RT.

Non-commercial 3D-to-3D solutions

EAMapReader. EAMapReader [20] is an extension of the open-source software 3D Slicer (version 5.0.3, www.slicer.org [70]), designed for 3D-to-3D registration between EAM data and CCTA. It supports vendor-specific formats from CARTO® 3, EnSite™ NavX™/Velocity™/Precision™, and RHYTHMIA HDx™ and is compatible with Windows, Mac OS, and Linux.

Within EAMapReader, the map geometry, electrophysiological data, and ablation tags or points of interest are displayed as 3D objects, allowing registration not only to CCTA but also to other DICOM modalities such as cardiac MRI or SPECT. This enables seamless integration of structural substrate data from advanced cardiac imaging with functional substrate information from electrophysiological studies.

The workflow involves segmenting of cardiovascular structures from the imported CCTA, [20] manually co-registering EAM data with LV endocardial structures and the ascending aorta, and optimizing alignment using an iterative closest point algorithm. The CardTV-EP is defined directly on a rendering of the CCTA and extended transmurally to generate the final CardTV. Additional imaging can refine the target in Slicer before exporting the CardTV as a DICOM-radiotherapy (RT) structure for TPS integration.

HeartMap. This Python-based 3D Slicer plugin extends EAMapReader's functionality by integrating ECGI (CardioInsight, Medtronic) data. [24] It streamlines operations with semi-automatic scar surface annotation, translating EAM and ECGI data into a 3D surface model. The arrhythmogenic substrate contours are perpendicularly extended by an arbitrary 2 mm to generate the CardTV. Registration functionalities in 3D Slicer rely on landmark-based, automatic iterative closest point, and manual refinement methods. The CCTA and final CardTV are exported as a DICOM-RT data set for TPS integration. In two STAR cases, volumetric Dice matching achieved 0.71. [24].

Additionally, Peichl et al. [18] reported a Python-based script converting.mesh to.vtk files, later using 3D Slicer to project the CardTV-EP to the CCTA following landmark registration and manual optimization.

MATLAB script-based solutions. Brett et al. developed an in-house MATLAB script to convert EAM data from.mesh to.vtk format, enabling compatibility with 3D Slicer. The arrhythmogenic target is overlaid on imaging, with a raised border added before 3D Slicer converts the volume into a DICOM file for TPS integration. [21] The code is

available in the online supplements. Accuracy data has not yet been published.

Oh et al. [59] created in-house software for converting non-DICOM EAM images from CARTO into DICOM structure files. The files contained nodes and faces of a triangular surface mesh with electrical activation formation, stored in an American Standard Code for Information Interchange format. Using the commercially available MIM Maestro software (MIM Software Inc., OH, USA), 3D EAM surface meshes are co-registered with six degrees of freedom to the segmented PCT (LV endocardial surface and cardiac substructures), cardiac MRI, or CCTA based on an iterative closest point algorithm, sometimes with manual optimization. This approach minimizes image registration errors, achieving a Dice similarity index of 0.81 ± 0.05 . After transmural expansion, the CardTV is generated.

However, neither system supports additional anatomical analyses, such as imaging-derived channel assessment or ECGI integration.

CardioMerge. Rigal et al. [60] developed CardioMerge, a C# software integrating a deep-learning-generated segmented CCTA, including LV wall thickness with EAM data using iterative closest point and manual optimization. CardioMerge uses the insight toolkit (<https://www.itk.org>) and visualization toolkit (<https://www.vtk.org>). Additional PET data can be rigidly merged. The method has been compared to manual (slice-by-slice) delineation by four electrophysiologists, reducing the interindividual variability with a Dice score of the resulting structures (0.32 vs. 0.62, manual vs. software). [60] There was high interobserver similarity for CTV delineation, 0.81 ± 0.11 . [61] This software has several limitations: it is compatible with only a single EAM vendor (CARTO® 3), is not commercially available, and lacks open-access availability.

Similarly, Dvorak et al. [62] relied on the visualization toolkit to convert the CARTO export for 3D Slicer using a C# software solution. This workflow depends on the distance and movement of the ICD lead and the irradiated target and uses a modified workflow from Peichl et al. [18].

A common limitation inherent to all approaches using the 3D Slicer

platform is the powerful 3D Slicer user interface, which is not very intuitive, leading to a steep learning curve when first using the software. Users require basic knowledge of coding to transform the EAM data with the STAR tags into files that are compatible with 3D Slicer. Thus, prior experience with quantitative imaging is an advantage, as is training, and supervision by an experienced user.

Direct EAM-TPS integration. Currently, commercially available radiotherapy TPS cannot directly integrate EAM data. Indirect integration requires investigational software scripts to display the EAM geometry, design the target in relation to this EAM data, and export the resulting target volume (CardTV-EP) as a DICOM-RTSS] or DICOM Segmentation (SEG) <https://www.dicomstandard.org/News-dir/ftsups/docs/sups/sup111.pdf> to be read into the radiotherapy TPS. Konermann et al. [63] developed a semi-automated tool “Edico” (Electroanatomic map Dicom Converter), which enables EAM import to the TPS by converting it to a DICOM file using voxels with a maximal size of $1.8 \times 1.8 \times 8$ mm with average voltage values of the data falling to the voxel. This software solution only supports the CARTO® 3 system. Because of direct integration, the Dice similarity coefficient is as high as 0.87–0.96.

Commercially available 3D-to-3D solutions

ADAS3D. ADAS3D (ADAS3D Medical SL, Barcelona, Spain) is a commercially available software for multimodal image integration and arrhythmogenic substrate analysis (Fig. 3). It enables co-registration of CCTA, 2D and 3D MRI, EAM, and ECGI data. [26,64].

ADAS3D supports importing of EAM from vendors including CARTO® 3, EnSite™ NavX™/Velocity™/Precision™, and RHYTHMIA HDx™. Imaging modalities can be registered via landmark-based, manual, or iterative closest point alignment, with real-time feedback on alignment accuracy. Auto-segmentation of cardiovascular structures from CCTA utilized on a robust machine learning pipeline, including a low-resolution binary LV mask and a multi-level segmentation mask. After artifact removal and post-processing, polygonal meshes are generated, facilitating ventricular wall thickness calculations. Further

Fig. 3. 3D-to-3D registration using the commercially-available software ADAS3D. Panel A. The electrophysiological characterization is performed by co-segregating all available 2D target-surfaces from the invasive and non-invasive electrophysiological studies, indicating VT-exit sites and VT isthmuses. Panel B. After co-registration of other imaging modalities (here cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA)), the 3D CardTV is generated by extending the target-surface relying on the CCTA-derived wall thickness model. The CardTV is exported as a DICOM-RT that can be imported in the planning CT. Adapted from Kaya et al. with permission. [26] Abbreviations as in the Graphical Abstract: AP, anteroposterior; LA, left atrium; LV, left ventricle; RA, right atrium; RV, right ventricle.

refinement of the CardTV-IMG is available through pixel signal intensity-defined tissue characterization from cardiac MRI. ADAS3D allows visualization of myocardial fibrosis, fatty infiltration, and calcification, all involved in bordering VT corridors. Additionally, adjacent structures, such as coronary vessels and the phrenic nerve, can be highlighted. The CardTV, defined through user annotations and voltage/activation data from EAM, can be displayed and color-coded within the CCTA-defined transmural myocardium, using an iterative trackball. In the investigational version of the software, the CardTV is exported as a DICOM-RT file for TPS integration. CardTV_{EP} delineation showed excellent interobserver agreement with faster and more robust workflows compared to 3D slicer. [71] ADAS3D also had a steep learning curve, an important factor given the limited use of STAR, even in high-volume VT ablation centers. In a case report, a high transfer accuracy was observed, with a mean error of 1.41 ± 1.03 mm when comparing the CardTV-RT from the PCT with the predefined CardTV in

ADAS. [26].

InHEART. The InHEART software-as-a-service platform (v1.1.1, InHEART, Pessac, France) offers segmentation capabilities for CCTA and MRI data (Fig. 4, Panels A-D). However, it does not support the import or integration of 2D EAM target surfaces. (Contrast-enhanced) CCTA or MRI are processed using MUSIC (Institut Hospitalo-Universitaire l'Institut de Rythmologie et Modélisation Cardiaque, University of Bordeaux, France; and Inria Sophia Antipolis, France) and segmented with proprietary algorithms. This segmentation provides critical insights into LV wall thinning, late iodine or gadolinium enhancement, coronary vessels, phrenic nerve positioning, myocardial fat, calcification, and thrombi.

A significant limitation is that electrophysiologists cannot adjust anatomical segmentations, which is crucial for STAR preparation. The InHEART imaging data export is compatible with major EAM systems

Fig. 4. 3D-to-3D registration using the commercially-available software InHEART Panel A. Transverse section of cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA) scan of a patient with non-ischemic cardiomyopathy and ventricular tachycardia with a septal exit. Panel B. 3D reconstruction including leads in the right atrium, right ventricle, coronary sinus, and basoseptal late-iodine enhancement (LIE, in dark pink). Panel C. 3D reconstruction of proposed CardTV (turquoise), including the septal scar. Of note, previous EAM maps are not co-segregated. Panel D. CCTA including CardTV for stereotactic radioablation. Abbreviations: Ao, aorta; CTV_{EP}, electrophysiologically defined arrhythmogenic ventricular tachycardia substrate; LA, left atrium; LIE, late iodine enhancement; LV, left ventricle; RA, right atrium; RV, right ventricle. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and 3D Slicer. In EAM systems, the CardTV can be propagated to the PCT using a side-by-side approach. In 3D Slicer, the CardTV is delineated on the CCTA surface, transmurally expanded, and exported as a DICOM-RT. [63] Alternatively, InHEART provides an anatomy-guided CardTV-IMG data set without EAM co-registration for STAR planning. This dataset can be annotated within the user interface and exported in a radiotherapy-compatible DICOM format. However, validation is lacking, and its use for nonischemic substrates is not recommended. [27].

Mimics innovation suite. The MIMIC Innovation Software platform (Materialise, Leuven, Belgium) enables the registration of DICOM images from CCTA with.vtk or.dif data from EAM or ECGI. [66] The platform is limited by its high costs and lack of additional anatomical or functional analyses. Currently, there is no data available on accuracy and reproducibility.

HoloLens integration. One case report highlights the use of augmented reality for interdisciplinary CardTV-RT refinement. CCTA segmentation, co-registered electrophysiological CARTO data, and TPS-derived structure sets were imported into the HoloLens 2 (Microsoft Inc.) for visualization and discussion. [67] InspirationLabs GmbH (HoloHeart, Heidelberg, Germany) developed software for data transformation, import, display, and 3D object handling in augmented reality.

Cross-validation results between different approaches

The first cross-validation of conceptually distinct software solutions for CTV delineation was conducted by Hohmann et al. as part of the RAVENTA study. [58] This study demonstrated a high level of agreement between two independent workflows: 2D-to-3D (CARDIO-RT) and 3D-to-3D (EAMapReader). The blinded comparisons across ten cases yielded nearly identical CTVs, despite the differences in the registration approaches. The median 3D-COM difference was 3.6 mm, and the median Dice coefficient was 0.84, [58] underscoring excellent concordance between the methods. Cross-validation studies involving additional workflows and software solutions are still pending.

Quality assurance and minimal requirements

Quality assurance (QA) procedures are well established in radiation therapy. Various legally defined (inter)national standards describe a minimum of QA procedures for the total treatment chain of the radiation therapy process. These are for example the performance of external audits and description of the commissioning process and tests regarding dose output, dose delivery, and radiographic imaging modalities. [72,73] For stereotactic radiotherapy, which requires high precision of the therapy planning and dose application, the minimum requirements for QA procedures are stricter than those of conventional radiotherapy. [74] Furthermore, stereotactic radiotherapy often relies on precise diagnostic imaging for target delineation. Interdisciplinary quality requirements and procedures for planning imaging, e.g., jointly with neuroradiology for intracranial MRI, [75] are well established.

Concerning STAR treatments, different, independent medical disciplines are involved in the therapy planning process. To ensure successful treatment, minimum quality requirements should be defined in each area: electrophysiology/cardiology, radiology, nuclear medicine and radiation oncology with respect to the special features of STAR. However, in the recently published EHRA and HRS consensus statement regarding “patient selection, VT substrate delineation, and data transfer for stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation”, the word “quality assurance” is only mentioned once in regard to deformable image registration. [27] No further recommendations are given, and clear guidance on QA of the entire STAR treatment chain is currently lacking.

In the review article of Chalkia et al., it is recommended to involve medical physicists and medical-physics experts at the beginning of STAR

implementation in the clinic for the development of an appropriate QA protocol. [76] End-to-end tests of the entire process are also required to assess geometric accuracy and dosimetric evaluation. [76] Instead of using simple phantoms, available in each radiotherapy department, it could be useful for STAR to use anthropomorphic or more complex phantoms adapted to the specific features of the treatment, although the commercial availability of such phantoms is still limited worldwide. Specific recommendations on the implementation of such procedures were not provided in the aforementioned review. [76] Nevertheless, the publications of specific prototypes and phantom solutions are increasing due to the rapid implementation of cardiac applications in radiation therapy. [16,77,78].

As part of the STOPSTORM.eu project, a comprehensive QA program was implemented for STAR. [15] Refined guidelines for contouring organs at risk and cardiac substructures, as well as treatment planning guidelines, are already published. [79,80] The guideline process for QA for several radiotherapy devices and imaging modalities is ongoing. The evaluation of treatment data in the STOPSTORM registry will show where quality standards are insufficient. This can lead to the refinement of unspecific defined requirements and the discovery of lacking recommendations.

For the special situation of the STAR target transfer from the EAM/structural imaging tools to the radiation oncology treatment planning, including different data formats and software solutions involved in this process, the QA of the entire target volume definition and transfer is essential. Eventually, this can only be covered and tested in system-specific end-to-end tests with suitable phantoms for electrophysiology and radiation therapy combined. Optimizing the workflow is crucial for each step by means of optimal morphological or functional visualization of the scar region and electrophysiological information from 3D-EAM. [81].

Conclusion

This review underscores the need for standardized CTV delineation, transfer workflows, and quality assurance. Currently, the arrhythmogenic VT substrates identified on EAM are transferred across imaging modalities into the planning CT scan, using various 2D-to-3D and 3D-to-3D target transfer methods, including commercial and in-house computer-aided tools. While existing software solutions are not yet approved, available data suggests they offer higher accuracy than manual transfer. The precision and reproducibility of CardTV transfer vary per workflow, with notable improvements in interobserver variability, as measured by Dice coefficients and center-of-mass localization, compared to manual or side-by-side transfer. However, challenges such as integration limitations, accessibility, labor intensity, expertise requirements, and the lack of clinical validation for efficacy and safety persist. These issues will be further explored within the STOPSTORM.eu consortium.

Future developments

As STAR is an emerging non-invasive bail-out treatment modality for patients with refractory VT despite catheter ablation and antiarrhythmic drug therapy, optimization of target definition will be an area of scientific investigation. For the CardTV, the integration of non-invasive approaches shows promise, though the workflow remains undefined. Advancements in structural imaging technologies, including contrast-enhanced, respiratory- and ECG-gated PCT, offer significant potential to identify anatomical sites critical for the VT trajectory, such as conducting channels, helping to refine the CardTV. Direct integration of multimodal imaging data (e.g., MRI, SPECT, CT) into the TPS, alongside the optimization of image registration—choosing the optimal cardiac phase and refining rigid versus deformable registration to PCT—is a key focus area. Additionally, cardiac motion data from 4D CCTA can be used to generate a cardiac ITV and incorporate anatomical details, such as

wall thickness, into the planning process. Finally, future endeavors to adopt cardiac and respiratory gating of the therapeutic radiation beams are being investigated but are currently not used clinically. Further safety and efficacy outcome studies are needed to confirm CardTV transfer accuracy, also including re-mapping or re-imaging studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rachel M.A. ter Bekke: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Stephan Hohmann:** Writing – original draft. **Jingyang Xie:** Validation, Writing – original draft. **Melanie Grehn:** Writing – original draft. **Karolien Verhoeven:** Writing – review & editing. **Paul G.A. Volders:** Writing – review & editing. **Casper Muhl:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Yeşim Selma Kaya:** Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Martin Manninger:** Writing – original draft. **Daniel Scherr:** Writing – review & editing. **Stefanie Corradini:** Writing – review & editing. **Achim Schweikard:** Writing – review & editing. **Robert Rademaker:** Writing – review & editing. **Wiert F. Hoeksema:** Writing – review & editing. **Luis Schiappacasse:** Writing – review & editing. **Lukáš Knybel:** Writing – review & editing. **Etienne Pruvot:** Writing – review & editing. **Pieter G. Postema:** Writing – review & editing. **Petr Pechl:** Writing – review & editing. **Jakub Cvek:** Writing – review & editing. **Katja Zeppenfeld:** Writing – review & editing. **Oliver Blanck:** Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Judit Boda-Heggemann:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: This study is part of the project “Standardized Treatment and Outcome Platform for Stereotactic Therapy of Re-Entrant Tachycardia by a Multidisciplinary (STOPSTORM) Consortium” that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 945119. The MUMC+ (RtB/PV/YSK) has a research contract with ADAS3D. PGP received a Dutch Heart Foundation grant (03–003-2021-T061). JBH (UHEI) received personal fees from EBAMED SA, grants from Elekta AB, and personal fees from AstraZeneca, all outside of the submitted work. MM received speaker fees / honoraria from Abbott, Bayer Healthcare, Biosense Webster, Biotronik, Amomed, AOP Orphan, Boston Scientific, Daiichi Sankyo, BMS/Pfizer and research grants from Biosense Webster and Abbott. All other authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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